

376. **Patients' perceptions of glucocorticoid therapy: international development of a Patient Reported Outcome (the Steroid PRO)**

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Background/Objectives: Glucocorticoid steroids (GCs) are widely used to treat inflammatory rheumatic diseases. GCs carry a wide range of adverse effects of concern to patients and clinicians. The objective of this study was to explore the impact of GC therapy on health-related quality of life (HRQoL) during treatment for rheumatic diseases, as a basis for development of a Patient-Reported Outcome Measure (PROM) to be used in clinical trials and practice.

Methods: Patients from the UK, USA and Australia who were treated with GCs in the last two years for a rheumatic condition were invited to take part in semi-structured qualitative interviews. A steering committee of patient research partners, clinicians and methodologists devised an initial conceptual framework, which informed interview prompts and cues. Interviews identified physical and psychological sympto and salient aspects of HRQoL in relation to treatment with GCs. Purposive sampling was used to include a range of demographic and disease features. The interview data were organised using NVivo, and inductive analysis identified initial themes and domains. Candidate questionnaire ite were developed and refined using cognitive interviewing, linguistic assessment, and input from patient research partners.

Results: Sixty semi-structured qualitative interviews were conducted (UK n=34, USA n=10, Australia n=16). Mean participant age was 58 years;39 (66.1%) were female. Detailed demographic and GC use information is provided in Table 1. The following initial domains were developed to identify key themes relating to treatment using GCs and their impact on HRQoL: benefits of steroids; physical symptoms; psychological symptoms; psychological impact of steroids; impact of steroids on participation; and impact of steroids on relationships. Forty-one

candidate questionnaire items were developed from the individual themes. These were tested and refined by piloting with patient research partners, iterative rounds of cognitive interviews with patients with a range of rheumatic conditions from the UK, USA and Australia, and a linguistic translatability assessment, to define a draft questionnaire. Conclusions: This international qualitative study underpins the development of candidate items for a treatment-specific PROM for patients with rheumatic diseases. This draft questionnaire is now ready for testing in an online large-scale survey to determine the final scale structure, any item reduction, and measurement properties.

Disclosures: None

Table 1: Demographic and glucocorticoid steroid use summary

Qualitative interviews – Demographics and GC use		UK n=34	Australia n=16	USA n=10	All Sites n=60	
Sex	Male	14	6	1	21	36%
	Female	20	10	9	39	66%
Ethnicity	Asian/Asian British	0	2	0	2	3%
	Black/African/Caribbean/ Black British	1	0	3	4	7%
	Mixed/Multiple ethnic groups	1	1	0	2	3%
	White	32	13	6	51	86%
	Other ethnic group	0	0	1	1	2%
Age	18-39	5	5	4	14	23%
	40-59	10	2	3	15	25%
	60-79	15	8	3	26	43%
	80+	4	1	0	5	8%
Mean age		61	56	50	58	(SD 17.01)
Rheumatic disease(s)	Systemic vasculitis	13	5	1	19	30%
	Inflammatory arthritis	14	1	1	16	25%
	Crystal arthropathy	0	0	2	2	3%
	Connective tissue disease	4	8	5	17	27%
	Other	7	2	1	10	16%
Oral GC dose in last 7 days	>=30mg / day	1	0	1	2	3%
	>7.5 mg and <30 mg / day	6	4	1	11	18%
	<=7.5 mg or less / day	14	5	5	24	40%
	No oral glucocorticoids	13	7	3	23	38%